

Overview of drug poisoning in early childhood in Colombia (2019-2024): A Secondary Data Analysis

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Abstract:

Objective: Drug poisoning in the pediatric population continues to be a preventable public health problem, especially in early childhood, given the greater vulnerability to accidental exposure to medications. However, systematic analyses of this population in Colombia have been limited to date. This study aims to analyze the trend in reports of drug poisoning in children under 5 years of age registered with Cisproquim® between 2019 and 2024.

Methods: Secondary analysis based on anonymized databases provided by Cisproquim® for the period 2019-2024. Records for children under 5 years of age were included, and duplicated and incomplete records were excluded. Univariate and bivariate statistical analysis was performed using the ANOVA model. This study is considered risk-free given its characteristics.

Results: A total of 4,137 reports were obtained. Most cases were in preschool-aged children (47.6%) during the year 2022 (20.1%). Acetaminophen (14%) administered orally (97.8%) was the most frequent cause, the severity of the events was predominantly mild (50.6%), and most occurred in unintentional circumstances (99.2%). The highest proportion of cases were recorded in urban areas (92.7%) and in level I care institutions (35.2%).

Conclusions: This study provides findings that support the need to implement prevention strategies and public policies that limit contact with medications at these ages. Future research is proposed to study the incidence of poisoning in this population in depth.

Keywords: Poisoning, drugs, pediatrics, infants

Introduction

Acute poisoning in the pediatric population represents a significant public health problem worldwide. Both irrational prescribing and the incorrect use of medications without medical advice are risk factors for acute poisoning. Children are very vulnerable to this type of incident due to several developmental factors such as their great curiosity, their tendency to imitate adult behavior, their inability to recognize the risks associated with ingesting potentially toxic substances, and their neurological immaturity^{1,2}.

Globally, pediatric poisoning has been a subject of ongoing interest due to its impact on the burden of disability, morbidity and mortality in this population. A secondary analysis of the 2021 Global Burden of Disease (GBD) study database, which aimed to assess the burden and temporal trends of childhood poisoning between 1990 and 2021, showed that the global burden of pediatric poisoning decreased by 29.25% during this period compared to previous years.

However, it was concluded that, although the gap between low- and high-income countries in relation to childhood poisoning has narrowed over time, children in developing countries continue to have a significantly higher burden of disability. Consequently, childhood poisoning in these contexts remains a significant problem¹.

Zahran T. et al. conducted a secondary analysis of the toxicology telephone service database of the American University of Beirut Medical Center, the capital city of Lebanon. Between 2015 and 2019, 209 exposures were recorded in pediatric patients between the ages of 0 and 19, of which 53.1% were female. Children under 5 years of age accounted for the majority of cases (67.0%), and the most common substances were analgesics (14.8%) and cardiovascular drugs (10.0%)³.

In Latin America, the picture is not dissimilar. In an observational study with a historical cohort design, the incidence of drug poisoning in children aged 0 to 12 years registered at the Toxicological Information and Assistance Center of Santa Catarina, a state in southern Brazil, was analyzed. An average annual incidence rate of 6 cases per 1,000 live births was reported, with most cases of poisoning occurring in girls aged 0 to 3 years, of mild severity and due to accidental ingestion of medications at home².

In Colombia, the situation is no different in cases of acute childhood poisoning. According to Colombia's Weekly Epidemiological Bulletin (BES) for August 2024, the incidence of acute poisoning increased between 2022 and 2024; most cases were suicide attempts and occurred most frequently in adolescents⁴. Additionally, in a retrospective observational study they aimed to describe the behavior of acute acetaminophen poisoning in children aged 0 to 12 years reported to the Public Health Surveillance System (SIVIGILA) in Colombia from 2016 to 2019, it was found that the highest proportion of cases corresponded to males, within the 0-5 age group, the main route of exposure was oral (100%), accidental exposure was the most frequent type (92.7%), and the home was the most frequently reported place of exposure (99.0%)⁵.

However, to date, systematic analyses describing the trend in recent years of drug poisoning in early childhood are limited in Colombia, especially in the period after 2019, which has been characterized by social and health changes resulting from the COVID-19 pandemic.

More than 30 years ago, the Colombian Safety Council created the Chemical Safety Information Center (Cisproquim®) to provide advice on the management of emergencies involving chemical substances in order to prevent or mitigate the consequences of such events⁶.

Intending to identify behaviors and providing useful evidence to guide future prevention strategies, this study aims to conduct a retrospective secondary analysis about the trend of acute drug poisoning reports in children under 5 years of age from 2019 to 2024 in Colombia, based on the Cisproquim® database.

Methodology

Study design

In this study, a descriptive and cross-sectional secondary analysis was performed using anonymized databases provided by the Chemical Safety Information Center – Cisproquim®, which is run by the Colombian Safety Council (CCS). The databases provided were initially

organized by year (2019, 2020, 2021, 2022, 2023, and 2024) and included records of patients of all ages. The records analyzed correspond to telephone calls received by that institution between 2019 and 2024 from different medical institutions, which were related to poisoning events in Colombia and neighboring regions.

Participants, measures, and hypotheses

For the study, variables such as patient characteristics given by sex and age in months, medication involved, chemical group classified using the Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical classification system (ATC), route of administration of the medication (inhalation, oral, cutaneous/mucocutaneous, ocular, otic, parenteral), severity measured by the expert opinion of a toxicologist contacted by telephone (mild, moderate, severe), intentionality and occurrence activity (intentional: criminal intent; unintentional: carelessness, misuse, and therapeutic error; others: adverse reactions and reactions due to chronic consumption) and, finally, geographic information of the event and its report (department of occurrence, area of the event: rural vs. urban origin, attention level provided by the institution consulted). See Annex 1. Table of variables.

Additionally, records of poisoning in children under 5 years of age (<5 years) involving Cisproquim® were established as inclusion criteria. Duplicate records and those with missing information on key variables such as age or agent involved were excluded.

Taking into account the type of population, the variables to be analyzed, and the particularities of the COVID-19 pandemic period, we consider that the results of this study will not show a significant increase in the number of cases reported during the lockdown period corresponding to the years 2020-2021, compared to the previous year and subsequent years. However, we do consider the possibility that the number of cases in this period may have increased. Additionally, we postulate that the most frequently implicated medications will be those commonly used in the pediatric population, such as acetaminophen, and medications commonly used in adults that can be easily found in the home, such as levothyroxine and antihistamines. Therefore, it is expected that the most frequently associated route of administration will be oral. Given the above, it is proposed that urban areas with greater access to medications will have a higher proportion of cases compared to rural areas. In relation to correlational results, it is presumed that the highest number of poisonings will occur in older infants and preschoolers compared to other age groups.

Statistical analysis

Data processing was performed by cleaning the data, taking into account the inclusion and exclusion criteria. The annual databases were subsequently consolidated using R Studio⁷ statistical software and Microsoft Excel. In addition, the database was adjusted by separating reports with multiple patients, thus avoiding data loss. Subsequently, with the cleaned databases, statistical analysis was performed at two levels: univariate and bivariate.

In the univariate analysis, absolute and relative frequencies were calculated for the qualitative variables, as well as measures of central tendency and dispersion for the quantitative variables. In the bivariate analysis, possible associations between variables were made, such as the relationship between age and severity of the event. These associations were evaluated using contingency tables, and the differences between the means were examined using one-way

analysis of variance (ANOVA), considering a statistical significance level of $p < 0.05$ and a 95% confidence interval.

Different graphs (frequency tables, bar charts, time series graphs) were used to visualize the data, in order to illustrate the distribution of cases and facilitate the identification of patterns.

Ethical considerations

Finally, it should be noted that this article used a completely anonymized database provided by the Chemical Safety Information Center (Cisproquim®), and therefore does not need to be submitted to an institutional ethics committee. Given the above, this study is considered risk-free in accordance with Resolution 08430 of 1993 of the Colombian Ministry⁸, which establishes the scientific, technical, and administrative standards for health research.

Results

The study obtained a total of 27,984 reported cases; however, 23,847 were excluded because they were five years old or older, resulting in a total population of 4,137 reports of drug poisoning in children under five years of age in Colombia in the period 2019- 2024. Table 1 presents the sociodemographic and clinical characteristics of the cases reported in the Cisproquim® database during this period.

Table 1. Sociodemographic and clinical characteristics of poisonings in children <5 years old, 2019-2024 (n=4,137).

Parameter	Number of cases	% of total cases
Total cases	4137	100
Gender		
Female	1958	47.3
Male	2179	52.7
Age (months)		
Newborns: 0-1	44	1.1
Young infants: 1-12	869	21
Older infants: 12-24	1256	30.4
Preschoolers: 24-48	1968	47.6
Date of event (year)		
2019	667	16.1
2020	594	14.4
2021	658	15.9
2022	833	20.1
2023	751	18.2
2024	634	15.3
Product involved*		
Acetaminophen	580	14.0
Levothyroxine	216	5.2
Metoclopramide	143	3.5

Parameter	Number of cases	% of total cases
Dihydrocodeine	113	2.7
Levonorgestrel-ethinyl estradiol	93	2.2
Tramadol	82	2.0
Cetirizine	79	1.9
Clonazepam	78	1.9
Montelukast	78	1.9
Chlorphenamine	75	1.8
Acetylsalicylic acid	74	1.8
Clozapine	70	1.7
Ferrous sulfate	67	1.6
Amoxicillin	64	1.5
Ibuprofen	62	1.5
Route of administration**		
Oral	4054	97.8
Parenteral	55	1.3
Cutaneous/mucocutaneous	17	0.4
Inhalation	16	0.4
Ocular	1	0
Optics	1	0
Unknown	1	0
Severity level***		
Mild	2095	50.6
Moderate	1737	42.0
Severe	255	6.2
None	50	1.2
Circumstance		
Intentional	2	0
Criminal intent	2	0
Unintentional	4102	99.2
Negligence	3742	90.5
Misuse	249	6
Therapeutic error	111	2.7
Other	33	0.8
Adverse reactions	31	0.8
Chronic intoxication	1	0
Withdrawal syndrome	1	0
Place of occurrence (area)		
Urban	3837	92.7

Parameter	Number of cases	% of total cases
Rural	300	7.3
Department of Colombia****		
Bogotá	778	18.8
Valle del Cauca	580	14
Santander	370	8.9
Antioquia	341	8.2
Atlántico	238	5.8
Cundinamarca	206	5.0
Risaralda	205	5.0
Córdoba	178	4.3
Sucre	147	3.6
Cauca	122	2.9
Caldas	111	2.7
Bolívar	106	2.6
Tolima	91	2.2
Huila	84	2.0
Nariño	77	1.9
Cesar	69	1.7
Goal	69	1.7
Guajira	55	1.3
Quindío	51	1.2
Boyacá	46	1.1
Magdalena	44	1.1
Norte de Santander	43	1.0
Putumayo	29	0.7
Casanare	21	0.5
Arauca	18	0.4
Caquetá	17	0.4
Guaviare	11	0.3
Guainía	7	0.2
Amazon	5	0.1
Choco	5	0.1
Others****	5	0.1
San Andrés, Providencia, and Santa Catalina	4	0.1
Vichada	3	0
Vaupés	1	0.1
Attention level provided by the institution consulted		
Level I	1457	35.2

Parameter	Number of cases	% of total cases
Level II	696	16.8
Level III	1108	26.8
Level IV	505	12.2
Not applicable	371	9.0

*Of all reports, only the 15 drugs with the highest cumulative frequency are included

**Some case reports had more than one route of administration

***The severity level (mild, moderate, severe) is classified according to the expert opinion of a toxicologist contacted by telephone

****Within the database, there are 5 cases reported from regions outside of Colombia

Source: Author's own elaboration

Most cases of poisoning occurred in males (52.7%), mainly of preschool age (47.6%). An increase in the trend of records was observed during 2022 (20.1%), with a subsequent drop in the frequency of poisonings for 2023 (18.2%) and 2024 (15.3%). Acetaminophen (14%) administered orally (97.8%) was the most frequent cause of poisoning, the severity of the events was predominantly mild (50.6%), and most events occurred in unintentional circumstances: carelessness, misuse, or therapeutic error (99.2%). Likewise, the highest proportion of cases was recorded in urban areas (92.7%), especially in Bogotá D.C. (18.8%), and in level I care institutions (35.2%).

The age of the population studied ranged from 0-48 months (0-4 years) and was characterized according to the three levels of severity (mild, moderate, and severe), finding that the age in months is not the same among the three levels of severity ($Pr(>F) = 0.00116$); which means there are statistically significant differences in the average age between the levels of severity. The mean age differs between the three levels of severity; in mild cases it is 28.7 months (SD: 12.7), in moderate cases 29.4 months (SD: 13.1), and in severe cases 26.2 months (SD: 14.7). Additionally, the median is 24 months (2 years) in all three severity levels; however, the interquartile ranges (IQR) differ: in mild and moderate cases, it is 12 months, and in severe cases, it is 24 months.

Table 2. Classes of drugs and main representative names.

	ATC classification	n	%	Main drug (n)
A	Gastrointestinal tract and metabolism	461	11.1	Metoclopramide (143)
B	Blood and hematopoietic organs	116	2.8	Ferrous sulfate (67)
C	Cardiovascular system	211	5.1	Losartan (46)
D	Dermatological	138	3.3	Crotamiton (20)
G	Genitourinary system and sex hormones	158	3.8	Levonorgestrel-ethinyl estradiol (93)
H	Systemic hormonal drugs	227	5.5	Levothyroxine (216)

ATC classification		n	%	Main drug (n)
J	Anti-infectives for systemic use	138	3.3	Amoxicillin (64)
L	Antineoplastic and immunomodulating agents	23	0.6	Methotrexate (3) Tamoxifen (3)
M	Musculoskeletal system	165	4.0	Ibuprofen (62)
N	Nervous system	1500	36.2	Acetaminophen (580)
P	Antiparasitic products, insecticides, and repellents	204	4.9	Benzyl benzoate (56)
R	Respiratory system	579	14.0	Cetirizine (79)
S	Sensory organs	59	1.4	Brimonidine (22)
V	Various	8	0.2	Methylthionine chloride (6)
	Not classified	31	0.7	
	Use of more than one drug or pharmacological classification involved	119	2.9	
Total		4137	100	

Source: Author's own elaboration

The most frequent chemical group was ATC-N: Nervous system (n=1500), whose main drug was Acetaminophen (n=580), followed by the chemical group ATC-R: Respiratory system (n=579), whose main drug was Cetirizine (n=79). Table 2 shows the cumulative frequency of the chemical group according to the ATC classification and its main representative drug. In several cases (n = 119), the use of more than one drug or pharmacological classification was recorded.

Figure 1. Trend in cases from 2019-2024 and their severity (n=4087).

Source: Author's own elaboration

* In this figure, the total number of cases (n=4,087) was taken, because cases classified as "none" (n=50) in the severity level were excluded.

Figure 1 shows the temporal distribution of reported cases of poisoning in children according to their severity level during the period 2019-2024. Throughout this period, the highest proportion of cases corresponded to the mild category (n=2095), with the highest number of records in 2019 (n=427), followed by 2022 (n=415). A change in the severity trend was observed, with an increase in moderate cases (n=1,737), particularly in 2023 (n=354) and 2024 (n=331). Finally, severe cases had the lowest cumulative frequency (n=255) compared to the other levels; their behavior remained constant until 2022, when they peaked (n=65), followed by a progressive decline in 2023 (n=61) and 2024 (n=43).

Figure 2. Cumulative frequencies of poisoning by the five most prevalent products and by population group during the period 2019-2024.

Source: Author's own elaboration

Figure 2 shows the cumulative frequencies of poisoning by the five most prevalent products according to the age group. In all age groups, acetaminophen was the drug with the highest cumulative frequency during all the years analyzed, with the highest frequency observed in 2023 ($n=65$) followed by 2022 ($n=64$), both in preschoolers.

Discussion

Drug-related poisoning has been identified as a topic of interest in public health due to its significant impact on the global population. However, despite the different strategies that have been implemented, it persists as one of the leading causes of morbidity and mortality in the pediatric population^{1,9-13}.

In the present study, after filtering and analyzing the anonymized database provided by Cisproquim®, reports of drug poisoning in males predominated, although the difference with respect to females was slight. Our results are consistent with the data reported by Zahran et al. (Lebanon)³, Marano et al. (Italy)¹⁴, and Lin et al. (Taiwan)¹⁵ in terms of gender distribution, where there was a slight predominance of males.

Additionally, in terms of other sociodemographic characteristics, in our study there was a higher report of cases in preschoolers (24-48 months), which is consistent with what has been found in the literature^{2,14-17}. This has been associated with the fact that children at this phase have reached developmental milestones that allow them to move around, handle medicine containers, and ingest the medication^{2,18}, supporting the hypothesis proposed.

Regarding the temporal trend during the period 2019-2024, it was found that the period with the highest cumulative frequency of poisonings occurred in 2022 (20.1%, $n=863$), followed by 2023 (19.2%, $n=751$). This trend aligns with the reports of the BES in Colombia published in

August 2024⁴, which also show an increase in acute poisonings in the years 2022-2024, suggesting that this phenomenon is not isolated but consistent nationwide and could be related to the aftermath of the COVID-19 pandemic¹⁹. However, this hypothesis lacks scientific evidence to confirm it, and may also have been caused by other unknown factors.

Considering the main chemical groups related to the toxicological accidents observed in this study, the class most involved was the nervous system (36.2%, n=1500). This finding is similar to that found by Brock et al. in an observational study conducted in Santa Catarina, Brazil, and by An et al.²⁰ in South Korea during a period of time similar to the one in this study, in which drugs belonging to the nervous system chemical group were the most frequent. Zahran et al., in their secondary analysis of the database of the toxicology telephone service of the American University of Beirut Medical Center, Lebanon, concluded that the most common substances were analgesics; similar to our study, where acetaminophen (14%, n=580), an analgesic and antipyretic, administered orally (97.8%, n=4054) were the most frequent cause of poisoning.

In terms of circumstances, unintentional poisoning (99.2%, n=4102) was the most frequent, which was also noted by other authors^{3,5,16}. These results highlight the need to take strict precautions in the Colombian population to prevent acute poisoning in early childhood, as children are more prone to accidental episodes.

The level of severity reported by the toxicologist was mild in most cases (50.6%, n=2095). Other studies have also recorded that most cases were asymptomatic or involved mild discomfort^{2,14,20,21}. This may be due to timely access to health services, rapid intervention by caregivers, low or subtoxic doses, and medications with a wide therapeutic margin.

On the other hand, in the present study, urban population accounts for 92.8% (n=3837) of cases, in contrast to rural areas, which accounts for only 7.2% (n=300). This suggests that in areas with greater availability of medications—especially those sold without a prescription—there is a clear need to strengthen and implement educational strategies on accidental consumption prevention, as well as measures to limit access to these products among the pediatric population.

In terms of geographical distribution across the country, the highest proportion of cases was found in the most populated departments: Bogotá D.C. (18.8%, n=778), Valle del Cauca (14%, n=580), Santander (8.9%, n=370), and Antioquia (8.2%, n=341). This may suggest that poisonings are related to the population density and volume of these territories, and for rural areas, it could be related to poor access to the health system and difficulties in reporting cases, leading to possible underreporting in these locations.

From a public health perspective, the results of this study highlight the importance of creating prevention policies and strategies that require the manufacture of safe packaging, as well as other specific interventions at each stage of development with the aim of reducing the incidence of poisoning in early childhood.

Limitations

This secondary analysis has some limitations encountered at the time of its completion. Among the main ones is its retrospective design, which may lead to inaccuracies given the loss of data in some reports. In addition, the use of a pre-existing database was considered, over which

there is no control over the primary data and its initial organization, which hindered subsequent data analysis. Furthermore, despite the severity being measured by the expert opinion of a toxicologist, no objective and validated scale of poisoning severity was used, which may lead to an underestimation or overestimation of the level of severity. Finally, it is considered that the reports were made voluntarily, so that unreported cases are lost. However, statistical analysis allows us to identify the trend in reports with a significant sample (n=4137) and in the Colombian population, which lacks in the literature to date, this being a strength.

Conclusions

Poisoning in the pediatric population continues to be a preventable public health problem. This secondary analysis found a trend of drug poisoning mainly in preschool children (24- 48 months), with a concentration of case reports in 2022. Additionally, oral acetaminophen was the most frequently implicated medication, and the predominant intent was unintentional (due to carelessness, misuse, or therapeutic error). This supports the previously proposed hypotheses and confirms that most poisonings are preventable.

This study provides findings that support the need to implement measures to limit access to medications in these age groups and guides the creation of prevention strategies and public health policies, including education campaigns for parents and caregivers, regulation of child-resistant packaging, and strengthening of toxicological surveillance systems. Additionally, emphasis is placed on encouraging case reporting and the importance of emergency response systems for poisonings. We emphasize in the need for future research to study the incidence of poisoning in the Colombian pediatric population in greater depth.

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Contribution

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References

1. Wang W, Yuan D, Yang F, Gao Y. Global, regional, and national burden of unintentional childhood poisoning, 1990–2021: an analysis of data from the Global Burden of Disease study 2021. *Front Public Health* [Internet]. 2025 Aug 5;13. Available from: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpubh.2025.1596599/full>
2. Brock K, Parma GOC, de Sá Soares A, Schuelter-Trevisol F. Analysis of notified drug poisoning among children in Santa Catarina state, 2016–2020. *Revista Paulista de Pediatria*. 2023;42(2).
3. El Zahran T, Mostafa H, Hamade H, Hitti E, Morgan BW, Kazzi Z. Toxicological exposures among the pediatric patients at a tertiary care center in Lebanon: the case for establishing a national poison center. *Clin Toxicol*. 2021;59(9):780–5.
4. Instituto Nacional de Salud (INS). Boletín Epidemiológico Semanal, año 19, semana 35: 25 al 31 de agosto de 2024. Bogotá: INS; 2024. [Internet]. [cited 2025 Sep 16]. Available from: https://www.ins.gov.co/buscar-eventos/BoletinEpidemiologico/2024_Boletin_epidemiologico_semana_35.pdf
5. Escobar Wilches DC. Comportamiento de las intoxicaciones agudas por acetaminofén en niños de 0 a 12 años reportadas al Sistema de Vigilancia en Salud Pública (Sivigila) en Colombia, 2016-2019 [Internet]. 2022 Sep. Available from: <https://epidemiologiains.org/index.php/ren/article/view/90>
6. Cisproquim® - ccs.org.co [Internet]. [cited 2025 Sep 16]. Available from: <https://ccs.org.co/cisproquim/>
7. RStudio Team. (2023). RStudio: Integrated Development Environment for R (Version 2023.06.1) [Computer software]. Posit Software, PBC. <https://posit.co>
8. Ministerio de Salud de Colombia. Resolución 8430 de 1993. Santafé de Bogotá D.C.; 1993.
9. Gordillo-Rodríguez L, Escobedo-Berumen L, Rendón-Macías ME, Garay-Carmona D, Blanco-Montero A, Vizcarra-Alvarado P, et al. Characteristics of pediatric patients admitted to intensive care due to severe intoxications. *Revista Mexicana de Pediatria*. 2022 Jan 1;89(1):12–8.
10. Matalova P, Buchta M, Drietomska V, Spicakova A, Wawruch M, Ondra P, et al. Acute drug intoxication in childhood: a 10-year retrospective observational single-centre study and case reports. *Biomedical Papers*. 2023;167(3):294–302.
11. Hoikka MH, Liisanantti JH, Dunder T. Acute poisoning in children under the age of six: A two-decade study of hospital admissions and trends. *Acta Paediatrica, International Journal of Paediatrics*. 2013;102(7).
12. Niccolas Bertote Guarda F, Nucci Galetti I, Regina dos Santos C, Marchioni C. Self-medication cases reported to a poison information center in Brazil from 2014 to 2020. *Clin Toxicol*. 2024;62(3):190–6.

13. Maior M da CLS, Osorio-de-Castro CGS, Andrade CLT de. Internações por intoxicações medicamentosas em crianças menores de cinco anos no Brasil, 2003-2012. *Epidemiol Serv Saude*. 2017 Oct 1;26(4):771–82.
14. Marano M, Rossi F, Ravà L, Khalil Ramla M, Pisani M, Bottari G, et al. Acute toxic exposures in children: analysis of a three year registry managed by a Pediatric poison control Center in Italy. *Ital J Pediatr*. 2021 Dec 1;47(1).
15. Lin CW, Chen WY, Lin YJ, Tsao PC, Lee YS, Juan CC, et al. Three decades of pediatric drug intoxication trends in Taiwan (1985-2020). *Journal of the Chinese Medical Association*. 2025 Apr 1;88(4):316–22.
16. Berta GN, Di Scipio F, Bosetti FM, Mognetti B, Mognetti B, Romano F, et al. Childhood acute poisoning in the Italian North-West area: A six-year retrospective study. *Ital J Pediatr*. 2020 Jun 11;46(1).
17. Lee J, Fan NC, Yao TC, Hsia SH, Lee EP, Huang JL, et al. Clinical spectrum of acute poisoning in children admitted to the pediatric emergency department. *Pediatr Neonatol*. 2019 Feb 1;60(1):59–67.
18. Sambuu T, Bayanbat BA, Naidan O, Badarch TU, Mukhtar Y, Ichikawa M. Home safety hazards associated with unintentional poisoning among children aged 0–5 years in Mongolia: A case–control study. *Tropical Medicine and International Health*. 2024 Apr 1;29(4):273–9.
19. An J, Ko Y, Yang H. Comparison of pediatric poisoning patterns before and during the COVID-19 pandemic in South Korea. *PLoS One*. 2024 Aug 1;19(8 August).
20. Bentur Y, ObchNIKOV ND, Cahana A, Kovler N, Bloom-Krasik A, Lavon O, et al. Pediatric poisonings in Israel: National Poison Center data. *Isr Med Assoc J*. 2010;12(9):554-9.
21. Vilke GM, Douglas DJ, Shipp H, Stepanski B, Smith A, Ray LU, et al. Pediatric poisonings in children younger than five years responded to by paramedics. *Journal of Emergency Medicine*. 2011 Sep;41(3):265–9.

Annex 1. Table of variables

Variable	Variable Type	Measurement scale	Role	Operationalization
Age	Cuantitative	Discrete	Independent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0-48 months
Age ranges	Cualitative	Ordinal	Independent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Newborns: 0-1 months • Young infants: 1-12 months • Older infants: 12-24 months

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preschoolers: 24-48 months
Gender	Cualitativa	Nominal	Independent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Masculine • Femenine
Year	Cuantitativa	Discreta	Independent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2019 • 2020 • 2021 • 2022 • 2023 • 2024
Place of occurrence (area)	Cualitativa	Nominal	Independent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rural • No rural
Country department	Cualitativa	Nominal	Independent	Colombia departamentos
Attention level provided by the institution consulted	Cualitativa	Ordinal	Independent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Level I • Level II • Level III • Level IV • Not applicable
Product/ Medicine	Cualitativa	Nominal	Dependent	5 most common products/medicines
Route of exposure	Cualitativa	Nominal	Independent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inhalation • Oral • Cutaneous/ mucocutaneous • Ocular • Otic • Parenteral • Unknown
Chemical group	Cualitativa	Nominal	Dependent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ATC-A: Alimentary tract and metabolism • ATC-B: Blood and blood forming organs • ATC-C: Cardiovascular system • ATC-D: Dermatological • ATC-G: Genito urinary system and sex hormones • ATC-H: Systemic hormonal preparations • ATC-J: Anti-infectives for systemic use

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ATC-L: Antineoplastic and immunomodulation agents • ATC-M: Musculo-skeletal system • ATC-N: Nervous system • ATC-P: Antiparasitic products, insecticides, and repellents • ATC-R: Respiratory system • ATC-S: Sensory organs • ATC-V: Various
Level of severity of intoxication	Cualitative	Ordinal	Dependent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mild • Moderate • Severe
Type of poisoning	Cualitative	Nominal	Independent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intentional: criminal intent • Unintentional: negligence, misuse, or therapeutic error • Other: adverse reactions, chronic use reaction, withdrawal syndrome